

INFLUENCE OF ELECTRONIC DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT ON ORGANIZATION MANAGEMENT

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Abstract. *This article examines the impact of electronic document management systems on the management of an organization using the example of a university. Automation of document flow can help improve the quality control of education and the control of the organization's activities as a whole. To address the problem of automating an electronic document management system, the issue of mathematical modeling of the system as a whole is considered, allowing for effective processing and transfer of the received document to the desired department.*

Keywords: *electronic document management, organization management, automation, implementation of document flow, subject, object.*

INTRODUCTION

In modern society, where there is a rapid growth of informatization in all areas, increasing the efficiency of management activities is becoming one of the priority areas for improving the activities of the organization as a whole. One effective way to increase the efficiency of the labor process is through automation. In most organizations, working with documents is complicated by the fact that their approval requires sign-off from not one, but several departments. To submit a document, management must contact various departments, which creates additional inconvenience. To solve this problem, we are currently using the full capabilities of the document automation system. The difficulties that arise when solving the problem of automated support for managing the processing and implementation of document flow are associated with its specific qualities. Automation and management of the document flow process were initially associated only with the automation of some auxiliary routine operations [1]. However, the rapid development of information technology and the emergence of fundamentally new classes of software products have led to the introduction of approaches to automating the management of organizations using mathematical modeling and the use of information technology. The formation and use of automation methods are directly related to the resolution of certain recognition problems of an applied nature using mathematical methods of a theoretical nature. At the same time, it is necessary to solve the problems of design, implementation, and operation of electronic document management systems, which are the basis for the automation of systems as a whole.

As a subsystem for automating the activities of an organization, the document flow system implies the automatic transfer of registration documents in accordance with the order of a certain path. For example, in organizations where an employee must approve a file, there are several departments for approval, and they move step by step from the lower department to the higher department, and only after receiving the approval of the lower department can the document be transferred to the higher department for approval [2]. The document flow system is designed to receive, recognize, and then send a document to the performing entities of the document flow system. The document goes to the required department for processing and approval. This document management system is more efficient, and documents are processed at a higher speed

compared to conventional methods. Compared with conventional document processing, a document management system significantly improves the efficiency and accuracy of document processing [3]. Once the user defines the processing path, there is no need to send the request to all departments and organizations. The system will automatically determine to whom to send a notification about the revised document. Currently, in almost all organizations, including higher educational institutions, a partial electronic document management system is widely used as a typical example of electronic document management, which does not allow for fully optimizing the operation of the document management system. Therefore, there is a need to maximize electronic document processing throughout the organization. Employees and system users can view their documents for processing and forwarding to the desired department. Employees can also view the documents they have processed and, depending on their status, receive various system orders [4].

Employees, depending on their position, can be divided into the following levels:

- system administrator;
- heads of organizations and departments;
- all other employees.

The main unit responsible for the clear organization of document flow in organizations is the object and subject responsible for the execution of documents. The main disadvantages when working with documents in organizations are the following [5]:

- insufficient quantity or outdated versions of normative and explanatory materials that make it possible to describe documentation support and documentation rules in organizations that take into account general laws, as well as regulations, both prescribed by higher authorities, and decrees of a given organization and internal departments;

- an unfinished approach to systematization in the implementation of typical issues, which is not effective and does not allow for timely execution of documents, especially concerning documents that require collective work, which can lead to unnecessary increases in the volume of stored information and, as a result, complicates the search for necessary data;

- the absence of or poorly organized unified transport and communication infrastructure that integrates document storage within the organization's departments, considering territorial separation;

- the use of systems that do not effectively and promptly respond to changes in the organization's documentation base.

Studies in the field of organizing the documentation process in some organizations have revealed several shortcomings in the centralization of document flow processing and the introduction of explanatory terms within the organization relevant to this issue. Typically, as a result of some organizations' efforts to implement their own methods for classifying documents and streamlining the document flow process, it leads to even greater workloads [6].

The implementation of an effective software complex for managing an organization leads to the optimization of the organization's document flow [7], contributing to effective work with large volumes of data, which significantly improves the organization of all processes, thereby enhancing the labor efficiency of the organization's employees. To achieve effective results from the implementation of new software complexes in the field of document management, it is necessary to define the technology of document flow.

Basic concepts:

“Document - a recorded piece of information on a material medium with requisites that allow it to be identified” [8].

Document flow (electronic document flow) – a system for the creation, editing, transfer, receipt, and archiving of documents in an organization from the moment of their creation or receipt until the completion of execution or dispatch.

An electronic document management system is a system that allows for controlling activities related to the reception and processing of documents and their further transfer to the necessary direction, as well as ensuring protection against unauthorized access.

Subjects in the document flow system refer to employees of a certain department of the organization who process documents. The responsibilities of the subject include receiving documents of a certain type, processing them, and sending them to the appropriate department.

The object in the document flow system is the organization, its departments, or a higher authority. In the document flow system, the subject is associated with a specific object of the system.

Regarding the term "document" as one of the components of document flow, we use the following definition:

“A document is any object that contains information used in the organization and the work process” [1].

Further, documents can be classified as follows:

- documents received from other organizations, involved in the document flow (incoming):
- documents not requiring a response;
- documents requiring a response;
- personal information;
- user requests;
- documents received from branches of organizations (subsidiaries, etc.);
- documents sent to other organizations (outgoing):
- documents created by employees of the organization and approved by the management (memos, orders, assignments, etc.), requiring registration in the document flow system (internal);

Fig.1. Document flow life cycle

Each document created in an organization is characterized by its existence, that is, its life cycle. Figure 1 shows the life cycle of documents and the implementation of documents for execution in organizations.

Materials and methods.

The implementation of a document for execution means the stage of its formation and execution. At the implementation stage, the document must be signed by the governing bodies of the enterprise and submitted for execution. At the registration stage, the document is registered in the office and submitted for execution, after which the document is submitted to the archive.

In the electronic document management system being developed, the first three categories include Decrees and resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, orders of rectors and vice-rectors. The fourth category includes documents of the department. These documents are classified based on keywords. Incoming documents are recognized based on keywords. Documents are divided into 4 categories. Each category has its own characteristics.

The organization level can include both a centralized document flow and one presented at the level of individual departments. In the process of working in a document management system, it is customary to distinguish three main types of documents: incoming (from external organizations), outgoing (from departments) and internal (for the purpose of transfer within the organization itself). The table below shows the documents of the university, the dean's office and the department as a whole.

TABLE. University documents

Data set	Department documents	Additional data
Student documents	Topics of theses and master's theses/coursework	
Planning the educational process of students	Monitoring assignments / documents that are used to test students' knowledge (bases of test questions, variants of assignments for testing, etc.)	report on the work done / Test rating
Scientific works	Reviews of scientific works, monographs, teaching aids	Diplomas, dissertations
Documents of teachers	Projects, cooperation with other organizations	Scientific articles of teachers of the department/Individual plans, work of department teachers
Documents of the department	Orders of the dean of the faculty and information on their implementation / Decisions of the University Council, Methodological Council, Faculty Academic Council (copy) Department reports	Plans of the department Instructions of the rector and vice-rectors of the university

Dean's office documents	Student data (performance, grades) /Department reports Department plans Dean's office plans	Student practice Graduates Minutes of faculty meetings Students' internships Students' final works Diploma
Rector's documents	University plans Agreements with foreign organizations, universities Agreements for internships abroad Approval of the annual curriculum	

Based on these and other documents submitted for execution, mathematical modeling of documents is carried out based on special keywords, very often characteristic of a given document. Document recognition is carried out using these keywords. At the same time, document modeling means that in an electronic document management system, instead of a document, only its model is used, which allows economical use of computer memory and document transfer time. For the effective operation of the electronic document management system, typical types of all documents that may be encountered in the organization are entered into the system in advance. Then, if necessary, the system can be supplemented with new documents. Modeling and recognition methods are carried out in other works.

Conclusion

As a result of the analysis of the above information from the organization using the example of a university, the need to create an electronic document management system with further effective management of the organization was justified. Electronic document management systems are the main system in the management of an organization. The use of such systems makes it possible to increase the efficiency of the organization's employees, reduce time costs, which ultimately can lead to an improvement in the organization's performance. There are three main tasks solved in electronic document management systems: documentation (document entry, joint execution of documents), organization of work with documents, document flow and structuring of document storage (search and organization of documents).

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